

Digital Platform Adoption in Educational Marketplaces: A Nepalese Perspective

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Abstract

Nepal's educational marketplaces include sellers of Syllabus books, stationery items, Montessori and science lab materials, digital gadgets, and various learning supplies, also providers of reading spaces, skills workshops. This study explores how these vendors adopt digital tools for E-catalogs, orders, payments, and customer support and how adoption of digital platforms affects their efficiency, service quality, and educational access.

For data collection a mixed-methods approach was used. A survey was conducted among fifty (n =50) respondents (20 vendors and 30 users) across urban and rural areas. Interviews taken with business owners and platform providers also collected real-world challenges. Quantitative analysis examined the factors such as vendor size, availability of Internet access, and perceived benefits in relation to adoption levels. Qualitative findings highlighted barriers (connectivity, costs and digital skills) and enablers (mobile apps, digital payments, simple interfaces).

Findings of this study show that vendors with reliable Internet and basic digital skills adopted platforms more quickly, users valued faster order processing, real-time stock visibility, and online payment and digital adoption reduced paperwork, improved order accuracy, and expanded reach to remote learners. These results suggest that modest investments in basic digital tools can help Nepal's educational marketplaces serve more learners, operate more efficiently, and reduce waste. The study offers clear recommendations for vendors, platform developers, and policymakers to support straightforward digital adoption and improve educational access across Nepal.

Keywords: *digital payments, digital literacy barriers, educational marketplaces, e-catalogs, operational efficiency*